

EU BON's contributions towards meeting Aichi Biodiversity Target 19

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Abstract

The EU BON (“Building the European Biodiversity Observation Network”) project has made important contributions towards the achievement of global conservation targets. This infographic illustrates EU BON's contributions towards the achievement of Aichi Biodiversity Target 19 “By 2020, knowledge, the science base and technologies relating to biodiversity, its values, functioning, status and trends, and the consequences of its loss, are improved, widely shared and transferred, and applied.”

Keywords

biodiversity, data, GBIF, EU BON, Aichi Target 19

EU BON's efforts (shown in blue colour) to improve the collation and sharing of biodiversity data have directly contributed to supporting a policy process. This was achieved by collating/sharing biodiversity data so as to make them available to all via the Global Biodiversity Facility (GBIF) which, in turn, produces an indicator entitled [Growth in Species Occurrence Records Accessible Through GBIF](#). This global indicator, curated by the [Biodiversity Indicators Partnership](#) (BIP) as part of a suite of global indicators, is used to track progress towards meeting Aichi Biodiversity Target 19. EU BON's specific contributions are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. EU BON's tools and services have improved the management and sharing of biodiversity data.	
Product/service name	Description
Pluto F	Workbench to mobilise and curate biodiversity data.
ARPHA-BioDiv	Toolbox for scholarly publishing and dissemination of biodiversity data.
TreatmentBank	Free and open service to convert, store and disseminate biodiversity data extracted from publications.
GBIF Integrated Publishing Toolkit (GBIF -IPT v2.3)	Free open source software that enables sharing biodiversity datasets through the GBIF network.
EU BON training	Trainings and workshops have further supported efforts to improve data management and data sharing practices.

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